

A Gelatin/Activated Carbon Multifunctional Coating for Future Edible Diagnostic Systems

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Abstract — Edible electronics aims to deliver safe-to-eat devices for gastrointestinal tract monitoring constituted by food-derived materials and therefore can be metabolised by the human body. However, identifying materials and processing methods for edible sensors and electronics remains an open challenge. Here we present an edible multifunctional composite coating produced by spray-coating an ink formulation of activated carbon (conductor) and commercial gelatin-based candy (binder) in a water-ethanol dispersant. The coating exhibits advantageous electronic properties, including conductivity ($\sim 50 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ resistivity), piezoresistivity, stretchability and temperature sensitivity. To demonstrate its versatility, the same composite formulation is used to deliver functional properties to a range of relevant electronic components, namely gating material for field-effect transistors, and strain, pressure, and temperature sensors.

Keywords — Edible electronics, green electronics, green sensors, edible sensors, conductive coatings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ingestible technologies are miniaturised swallowable devices that can navigate the gastrointestinal (GI) tract and gather diagnostic data [1 – 4]. The global market for ingestible technologies reached USD 819.0 million in 2022 and is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate of 10.9% till 2030 as the demand for non-invasive diagnostics grows [5]. As the market expands, further research is required to address the associated retention risks of current implementations, which can therefore only be deployed in healthcare settings [2, 6]. Thus, although ingestible technologies greatly improve on traditional invasive methods, they do not reduce the hospitalisation burden and cannot be deployed at the point-of-care (POC) [7]. The associated health risks of ingestible technologies are mainly related to the materials typically employed in these systems, which are non-degradable, rigid, and potentially toxic (e.g. heavy metals and traditional batteries) albeit encapsulated [4 – 10]. Besides, the non-degradability nature of these single-use systems opens sustainability concerns about e-waste accumulation [11, 12].

Edible electronics is an emerging research area aiming at delivering electronic devices using food-derived materials [13 – 15]. The inherent safety and degradability of these materials are particularly advantageous for GI tract monitoring applications. By controlling the degradation rate of the components, edible systems can be completely metabolised by the body after performing a specific task, leaving no electronic waste, eliminating associated health risks and thus removing the need for hospitalisation. Such edible systems would enable POC testing of the GI tract. Although many edible devices have already been documented [13– 22], identifying materials with fundamental electronics properties, such as conductors, and relative processing methods for edible electronics remains

an open challenge [14]. Electronic conduction is possible for many edible metals (gold, silver, zinc, calcium) but they can only be eaten in small quantities (μg per kg of body weight per day) [16]. Activated carbon (AC, E 153) is emerging as an interesting electrical conductor for edible electronics as EFSA approves it as a food additive, can be eaten in relatively large quantities (mg per kg of body weight per day), is widely accessible and affordable [17]. Additionally, AC resistivity is temperature-dependent with a negative temperature coefficient (NTC), which is particularly interesting for temperature sensing applications [18].

In this work, we present a multifunctional edible composite coating constituted of only food-grade materials, namely AC (conductor), commercial Haribo® gelatin-based candies (binder), and water-ethanol (dispersant) (Fig 1a). The composite material can be easily deposited by spray deposition, which is compatible with many substrates. Its preparation process is simple, low-cost, and does not require sophisticated equipment. The coating exhibits advantageous electronic properties, namely electrical conductivity, piezoresistivity, and NTC. These features are exploited in several proof-of-concept applications. The conductivity of the material is first characterised and then leveraged to produce AC-gated organic field-effect transistors (OFET). The piezoresistivity and stretchability are instead exploited to produce strain sensors with an average gauge factor of 88.3, which is comparable to the state-of-the-art, and pressure sensors. Finally, an NTC thermistor is demonstrated. The novelty of this work relies on using the same material and deposition technique to realise several edible sensors, with performance comparable to state of the art, that can find direct application in future edible systems for GI tract monitoring.

II. RESULTS

A. Material Formulation and Deposition

The ink was prepared by first dissolving Haribo® gummies in deionized water at a concentration of 0.08 g/mL at 80 °C under magnetic stirring. Ethanol – an environmentally friendly solvent – was then added to the solution in a volume ratio of 7:1, creating a suspension of gummy nanoparticles. To assess the possibility of creating percolation pathways for charge carriers, AC was then added to the suspension with filler:binder weight ratio from 25 % up to 200%. The suspension was then tip-sonicated for 15 min (Branson Ultrasonics 450, titanium probe 101-148-070) and sprayed onto the target substrate using a custom spray-coating setup with a 750 μm nozzle (Paasche VL Series) supplied with compressed air (2 bar) through an aluminium mask – Fig 1b. The inks were freshly prepared before deposition and samples were produced with a fixed ink volume per unit area (0.6 mL/cm²).

Fig. 1. (a) Materials: the edible ink consists of AC, Haribo® candy, water and ethanol. (b) Spray-coating setup. (c) Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) of the produced coating with 200% AC loading. (d) Average sheet resistance (blue) and thickness (red) of the composite vs AC loading over three samples. (e) OFETs produced using this AC formulation (blue) vs using PEDOT:PSS (red) as gating material. Measured at $V_{ds} = -40$ V (f) Average resistance variation and standard deviations vs strain for over three identical strain sensors. (g) Bode diagram (modulus) for the impedance of the electrodes, the complete sensor (h = 500 μm) and the sensor with applied pressure levels (phase diagram was omitted). (h) Average relative resistance variation vs RH at a constant temperature (25 °C) of the pristine material (black) and encapsulated (red) over three identical samples. (i) Relative resistance variation vs temperature; black: average over three identical samples of the pristine material deposited on glass measured at a constant RH (15%); red: average over three identical thermistors measured at a variable RH.

B. Electrical Characterisation and FET Gating

The micromorphology of the edible coating deposited onto PDMS is irregular due to the AC size in the range of 10–100 μm (Fig 1c). The thickness of the coating was determined by microscopy analysis to be between 25–50 μm. (Fig 1d). The sheet resistance of the material was investigated at different AC loadings and fully characterized in related works [17, 19]. Sheet resistance was measured using a semiconductor parameter analyzer (Keysight B1500A) in a four-probe configuration. Effective percolation was reached with AC loadings between 25–50%, albeit with further increase of the AC loading the sheet resistance was reduced (Fig 1d). In particular, the average sheet resistance and resistivity with

200% AC loading were 11.8 ± 3.6 kΩ/sq and 53.8 ± 16.6 Ω·cm, respectively. An additional increase in the AC loading created low adhesion with the substrate. As such, the 200% AC coating, hereafter referred to as AC coating, was adopted for the following applications. As a proof-of-concept in organic electronics, the AC coating was used as the gating material of a top-gate bottom-contacts organic field-effect transistor (OFET). AC holds great potential in biosensing as carbon materials benefit from a large surface area and, therefore, are commonly employed for bioreagent functionalization, such as enzymes [23–25] or antibodies [26]. In our test case, we used cumulenic sp-hybridized carbon wires, in particular tetraphenyl butatriene ([3]Ph), as semiconductor and we tested the use of AC gate against using

PEDOT:PSS ($L = 20 \mu\text{m}$, $W = 2 \text{ cm}$). The AC and PEDOT:PSS transistors were characterized using the Keysight B1500A. AC-gated OFETs showed a comparable behaviour to PEDOT:PSS-gated ones (Fig 1e), although an increase in the gate current was observed probably related to the additional spray-coating fabrication step. Furthermore, the AC-gated devices produced a more stable response against photodegradation as AC provided effective shielding to light radiation, which is relevant for several organic semiconductors, as shown in [27]. The measured conductivity of the AC coating and its demonstration within an active device holds great potential for the adoption of this material for circuits and biosensors operating within the GI tract.

C. Strain and Pressure Sensors

The presence of the gelatin-based binder imparts a certain degree of stretchability to the coating, and piezoresistivity was observed when the coating was subjected to mechanical deformation. SEM analysis under strain indicated that the piezoresistivity mechanism is based on microcracks formation. Thus, the piezoresistivity property of this composite material was exploited to produce strain sensors by direct spray-deposition of the AC formulation onto PDMS dog-bone-shaped substrates. To characterize the sensors, the resistance of the device was measured using a National Instrument DAQ unit (NIUSB-6211) during increasing strain (Hongjin testing machine, 1 mm/min pull rate). The strain sensor exhibited an average gauge factor of 88.2 in the 0 – 8 % strain range (Fig 1f), which is comparable to state-of-the-art strain sensors implemented using graphene or CNTs [28]. Hence, fully edible strain sensors were implemented by substituting PDMS with edible stretchable substrates with gauge factor in the range 19 - 92 as documented in [17].

The stretchability and piezoresistivity of the composite coating were also exploited to develop an edible pressure sensor [29]. Starting from pressure-induced contact-resistance pressure sensors [30 - 32], we substituted each material with edible equivalents. In particular, we used gold (E 175) to produce bottom interdigitated contacts, ethyl cellulose (E 462) as the substrate, a gelatin/glycerol hydrogel diaphragm and the AC formulation as a stretchable electrode onto the diagram. With no applied pressure, the sensor is an open circuit (see Fig 1g measured using a MultiPalmSens4 potentiostat). As pressure is applied above a certain threshold, the diaphragm deforms and, when contact is established between the AC coating and the gold electrodes, the sensor switches to a resistive behaviour producing a variation of the impedance modulus of several orders of magnitude (Fig 1g). Changing the height of the diaphragm affects the pressure threshold: with a height of 500 μm and 1 mm, the pressure threshold was in the range 20.3 – 25.3 g/cm^2 and 50.3 – 57.9 g/cm^2 , respectively. Once over the threshold, the sensor is still sensitive to pressure increment as the contact area between the gold electrodes and the AC coating progressively increases. In a pressure range of 25.3 – 30.3 g/cm^2 , the device with $h = 500 \mu\text{m}$ showed a sensitivity of $-544.3 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{g}$. The piezoresistive strain and pressure sensors herein described can be directly operated using a direct current energy source such as batteries [22] and could be employed in future edible systems for peristaltic movement monitoring.

D. Temperature Sensing

AC is known to be sensitive to temperature [18] and humidity [33]. Therefore, temperature and humidity effects for the present AC formulation were analysed using an environmental chamber (Memmert HPP110eco). The resistance of the coating (measured using a source meter Keithley 2612A) increased by increasing the relative humidity (RH) at constant temperature (25 °C), with relative resistance variations up to 20% – see Fig 1h. Hysteresis was also observed, indicating a possible difference in the rates of adsorption and desorption of moisture in the material. At constant RH, the resistance of the exposed composite decreased when increasing temperature, i.e. NTC behaviour was observed (Fig 1i), with a temperature coefficient of $\alpha = -4.7 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ calculated as:

$$R = R_{\text{ref}} \cdot [1 + \alpha(T - T_{\text{ref}})] \quad (1)$$

The hysteresis was quantified to be 1.8 % at 25 °C. By linear fitting of the curve ($R^2 = 0.956$), a sensitivity of $-0.49 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ was determined. To enable the use of this composite for resistive temperature sensing, the humidity effect must be decoupled by temperature. A fully edible thermistor was implemented by encapsulating the coating using ethyl cellulose and beeswax (E 901), and accessing the material by two gold electrodes produced from an edible gold foil. The fabrication technique is successful in preventing humidity effects as virtually no effects were observed – see Fig 1h. The calibration curve of the thermistor was similarly obtained in a range of 5 – 50 °C with no humidity control as shown in Fig 1i. The thermistor showed a negative temperature coefficient of $\alpha = -2.9 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, hysteresis of 0.82% at 25 °C, sensitivity of $-0.32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, and linearity of $R^2 = 0.919$. The sensor showed analogous functional output when compared to commercially available components, as demonstrated in [21]. Our edible resistive temperature sensor is directly compatible with batteries and could be deployed in edible systems to monitor the GI temperature, which has been linked to infection or inflammation status [34].

III. CONCLUSIONS

Edible systems have the potential to enable POC testing of the GI tract by delivering miniaturised, portable, automated and – most importantly - safe devices for GI tract diagnostics. Here we demonstrate a formulation of an edible coating that can be used for a variety of physical sensors. AC ink was demonstrated to be an effective material for gating FET and holds great potential for edible circuits and biosensors. Also, strain and pressure sensors herein shown take advantage of the piezoresistivity and the stretchability of the composite material. Finally, the temperature sensitivity of the material was explored to deliver an NTC thermistor. All the sensors herein produced are directly compatible with edible energy sources and can provide diagnostically relevant information on the GI tract. The functional material presented opens the door to new application scenarios including agrifood technology, food quality monitoring/storage, diagnostic food, and edible robots.

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